

1. Introduction

In particular, in a context of increasing the level of markets openness, the leaders of certain domestic markets, including in the construction industry, may cede ground and lose the competitive position to new, innovative companies with more adaptive, flexible development strategies. Determination of a certain spectrum of development strategies, which will be further substantiated, is related to the need to understand their types, classifications by certain features and characteristics. In this area, there is a wide range of scientific researches, they need to be systematized and the provisions must be singled out, allowing the definition of a unified approach to possible types of strategies for the development of economic systems, depending on any given features, their characteristics, etc.

2. Materials and Methods

The presented author's list of types of development strategies of the entity in the industry is formulated on the basis of the use of comparative, analytical methods, and the system analysis method.

3. Results

One can distinguish a local approach to the classification of development strategies, which is associated with their systematization, depending on the evidences of a focus on the nature of market positions (change in the market share), the scale, area of operation in different spheres (growth either in the volume of activities, volumes of consumption of resources, costs, organizational external integration, etc.), produce policy. Local development strategies envisage outlining the areas of activity and performance benchmarks, the ways of reaching them narrowly, without covering the strategic management of all areas of the entity's activity. This category of strategies may vary, depending on the emergence of new scientific developments, practice-oriented examples of their identification and implementation in various fields. In particular, certain development strategies, applied in science and practice in early 20's, are not relevant in the 21st century, taking into account social and information changes.

In the framework of this approach, one should consider the content and characteristics of local development strategies, presented in the scientific research findings of O. Pashchenko [3]. The author investigates this problem through the example of a business entity (a company). The study of the materials of the research paper by the author showed that she identified the

LIST AND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MAIN DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES

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Abstract: There is widespread the agreement among scientists that development is a multidimensional phenomenon, with economic, political, and social aspects, and that the different dimensions of development are interconnected with one another in complex ways. The fact that these different dimensions exert causal influences on one another would suggest that policymakers, dealing with issues of national development need to integrate economic, political, and social approaches, and to think strategically about how to achieve their goals.

Strategic thinking implies prioritization and sequencing, seeking to do first that is necessary or helpful to achieve later goals.

A strategy begins by defining a clear objective, and then assesses constraints that prevent the achievement of this objective. Strategic thinking looks at alternative pathways that get around those constraints; if this is not possible, it requires the redirection of energies to other goals that are more realistically achievable [1, 2]. In the current conditions, one of the decisive aspects of the functioning of economic systems (enterprises, industries, economics) is the choice of the areas of development, designed and substantiated at the strategic level within the framework of a certain management entity. The need for the most appropriate and optimal choice of development strategies is actualized through the continuous influence of the environment, which is undergoing more rapid changes in the 21 century, has rather complex manifestations, associated with new globalization, information and communication challenges.

The scientific novelty of the proposed approach is that we take into account the best scientific interpretations regarding this issue, universalize the provisions of contemporary scientific thought in the definite aspect of the study, point out the innovative areas characteristic of the practice of the entities activity in the industry.

Keywords: development, construction, strategy, approach, classification.

following types of local development strategies of a business entity, namely:

1) types of development strategies, envisaging concentrated growth, including:

- strategies for increasing the market positions. Such strategies, as the author states, are implemented in the conditions of: developed markets; existing product portfolio; advanced technologies; the existence of certain market positions of the business entity. Among the main areas of such strategies will be those, related to the development and positioning of market position improvements through the horizontal integration, etc.;

- strategies, related to the development of markets. According to O. Pashchenko, such strategies can be implemented in the following conditions: new markets; existing product portfolio; advanced technologies; the existence of certain market positions of the entity. In the context of the key areas of the specified type of strategy, the ones, determining the search for new client segments (market space), can be distinguished;

- strategies, related to the development of the product range (development, positioning, promotion and marketing of new types of products (services)), etc. According to the researcher's approach, these strategies can be implemented under the following conditions, namely: a developed market space; new product (service); advanced technologies; the existence of certain market positions of the business

entity. O. Paschenko [3] refers to the development of new prospects and opportunities in terms of key areas of such strategies. In our opinion, this definition is somewhat simplified, it does not highlight the process component of developing, creating, promoting and marketing new products (services), adapting these processes and their elements to the environment changes, etc.

Such a strategy can be implemented under the following conditions, namely: the creation of new markets; use of a new product portfolio; application of new or existing technologies; independent creation of market positions of the business entity. Among the areas of implementation of this strategy may be the independent creation of all necessary conditions for the development and promotion of new types of products (services). Undoubtedly, this is a complex, risky area of development, but it is revolutionary, and with the systemic consideration of all environmental changes, it can become quite effective;

2) the types of development strategies that provide for integrated growth are:

– the strategies of reverse vertical integration. Among the main conditions of their implementation, according to the author [3], one can identify the following: the use of the existing market environment, products (services) and technological state of the entity; creation of new market positions in the market. The indicated strategies can be implemented in the area of the integrated association with the market entities, acting in the supply of goods, works (services), etc.;

– the strategies for direct vertical integration. The conditions for implementing these strategies, according to the researcher's approach [3], include the following: use of existing market environment, products (services) and technical state of the entity; creation of new market positions in the market. The outlined strategies can be implemented in the field of an integrated association with the market entities, being the intermediaries.

We would like to note that in modern conditions it is possible to use the development strategies that provide for integrated growth, and for the unions of competitors (including network and centralized ones) [4, 5]. Creation of such integration associations is possible in any industry, including construction (for example, the MTM-System Group of Companies (Kharkiv), founded on the basis of an association of Ukrainian and German construction companies, other companies in related fields [6]). Modern globalization processes, crisis phenomena or market priorities in the long run can promote the development of new integration associations on such conditions and with a composition of participants that were not traditional in the past. Among the new members may be the individuals, companies, associations, groups that are managed independently or at the level of other individual members, the structural units, which will consist of robots, controlled by humans or robots. All these new developments arise due to the changes in the environment, affecting the competitive position, and condition the development of both companies, industries, and the entire economy of the country, associations of countries, etc.;

3) types of development strategies that provide for diversified growth and include centralized, horizontal, and conglomerate diversification. The indicated development strategies are related to the strategic benchmark for the creation of diversification at different levels, in relation to any given spheres of activity. The most widespread one is the diversification of products, focused on targeted growth in certain markets;

4) the types of development strategies, related to the reduction of activities, costs. Such strategies, according to O. Pashchenko's fair point [3], relate both to productive ways of optimizing costs and to overcoming the situations, caused by the economic crisis. In certain cases, for example, under conditions of effective cost optimization, the economic growth may be possible with a corresponding increase in volumes of production, sales, promotion, market share, etc.

It is important to analyse the classification and characteristics of the development strategies identified by T. Starshynova, N. Perepelytsia [7]. According to the research, such strategies may be presented, in particular, by:

1) corporate development strategies that include: portfolio strategies (with an appropriate strategic plan for the development, promotion, marketing of the range of products of the company, a strategic program for using the company's investment portfolio), growth strategies (mainly those, identified in the framework of the traditional approach, namely: strategies of concentration, diversification and integration), competitive strategies (a wide range of strategies for raising the market position of companies). The category of strategies under study is

one of the priority and fundamental ones, which all others are adjusted to in large corporations, such as the leading American building corporation Lennar Corp. In particular, the priority corporate strategy of Lennar Corp. for the last five years (late 2018) was a territorial strategy of merger of competitors in the USA [8, 9]. Other structural strategies of the company development were adjusted to this strategy, particularly, the operational, business, etc.;

2) business development strategies (business strategies), represented by the local strategic plans to conquer strong long-term competitive positions of the company. According to T. Starshynova, N. Perepelytsia [7, p. 137], these are presented by the approaches, the trends that are being developed at the level of management to achieve the performance indicators in a certain, specific scope of activities (in particular, the development of projects eco start-houses, their promotion and sale within a particular region, etc.). As noted by the authors [7, p. 137], the economic entities, operating in one area (for example, the construction of filling stations, corporate and business strategies), may coincide. This is due to the fact that for such companies the development of a strategic plan and its justification are envisaged only in terms of a certain type of activity. At the same time, if the entities are engaged in multidisciplinary activities, even within a certain sphere of economic activity (particularly, the construction of filling stations, office buildings and shopping centres, residential buildings, etc.), such companies can be considered diversified, and they usually have both corporate and a number of business strategies.

4. Discussion

In our view, according to the approach [3] the composition of strategies that provide for concentrated growth can be expanded by the strategy, related to the promotion of new products (services) in emerging markets [4, 5]. This type of strategy is fully in line with the selected categories, also taking into account the demand for the new products (services) within the demand among the innovation-oriented consumers, such a development strategy can be implemented. In particular, in the construction sector, this concerns the construction and implementation of start-apartments, start-offices, which are in increasing demand among a sufficiently large share of consumers.

We can state that the approach of O. Pashchenko [3] is a systematic, integrated consideration of a sufficiently wide range of local development strategies, associated with the main features that determine their economic nature. The list of these strategies can be considered basic, fundamental, on the basis of which it is possible to implement certain modifications under the influence of performance benchmarks, environmental conditions, etc.

We would like to note that business development strategies, according [7], are both local to the enterprises, operating in the same field of activity, and particularly local for the companies, engaged in multidisciplinary activities [4, 5]. At the same time, the effectiveness of the business entities operation in each individual area depends both on the overall complex of strategic management, and on the effectiveness of business strategies in these areas, the professionalism of justifying the mechanism for their implementation, etc.

Systematization and study of modern scientific papers on the studied issues allowed the formulation of the author's approach to the problem of classification of the main strategies of an economic entity development [10, 11]. Namely, the main types of strategies of the entity development in the industry may include as follows:

1) local development strategies, which are identified by the functional (process), structural and managerial, market and product, financial and economic benchmarks and opportunities;

2) innovative local development strategies, conditioning the management of all (specific) spheres of activity and are related to the focus on the improvement of existing positions in all (specific) areas of activity;

3) comprehensive steady development strategies that represent optimal combinations of local sustainable development strategies;

4) comprehensive flexible development strategies that incorporate optimal combinations of local flexible development strategies and are most adapted to changes in the market environment, are the designers of its transformations, identify new trends and tendencies, and so on.

The scientific novelty of the proposed approach is that we take into account the best scientific interpretations, regarding this issue, universalize the provisions of contemporary scientific thought in the definite aspect of the study, point out the innovative areas characteristic of the practice of the entities activity in the industry.

Within the framework of the study, the main scientific approaches to the classification and characteristics of modern strategies of the economic entities development have been investigated. Among such approaches the following have been identified:

– the local approach to the classification of development strategies, associated with their systematization, depending on the features of a reference point to the nature of market positions (change in the market share), scale, trends of operation in different spheres, produce policy;

– the approach to the classification of development strategies, formulated in the context of their division by stages of the life cycle of products (services), focus of activities;

– the approach to the classification of development strategies, associated with their multi-level structuring within the framework of the economic entity operation;

– the approach to the classification of development strategies in the context of a company adaptation to the external and internal environment;

– the approaches that provide for the identification of strategies of the economic entities development, depending on certain essential features that characterize the selected strategic guidelines;

– the approach that involves the existence of integrated strategies for the development of economic entities, formed by certain local strategies.

Guided by the systematization of the provisions of scientific works, on the basis of studying the practice of the entities operation in the industry, an author's approach has been developed to determine the list of main types of strategies of the entity development in the industry.

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